

AZ

CA

CO

ID

MT

NM

NV

OR

UT

WA

WY

AZ**Fire size**

CA

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

CO

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

ID**Fire size**

MT

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

NM

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

NV

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

OR

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

UT

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

WA

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

WY

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

Prop. area burned: 1999-2020

Proportion of total

Prop. of projected IM costs: 1999-2020

Proportion of total